

DEX – Digital Employee Experience at Digital Workplace; Challenges and Strategic Implications for Organization Practicality

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Digital Employee Experience (DEX) refers to the experience of employees while interacting with the workplace technology, digital tools, information technology systems and infrastructure. The experience is not only focusing the technology infrastructure and applications, but also mainly focusing on the intuitiveness, supportiveness and efficiency of the technology tools in helping the employees performing everyday duties and tasks. The study plans to discuss the employee experience in the digital workplace and its importance for efficient organization functioning and to discuss the practicality of the organizations in challenges. There are a few studies has dealt with DEX in a qualitative way of discussion. This study applied qualitative approach using literature survey method to collect the existing literatures related to DEX and sustainable digital workplace for sustainability of the organizations. The study adopted qualitative literature review content analysis using summative method for discussing and reporting. The study explored the digital workplace tools for Collaboration and communication – Slack, Google Hangouts, Face book in workplace, for Project Management – Base camp, Asana, Trello, Write, for Remote Desktop – AnyDesk, Chrome Remote Desktop, Remote PC, for Time Management –Toggl, Clockify, Harvest, for Screen Sharing and recording –Team Viewer, Screen leap, Join .me, for Video Conferencing & Tele working – Skype, Zoom, Cisco Webex, and for Cloud Storage - Google Drive, Google Docs, Dropbox, One Drive. The study identified challenges like integrating business needs with business operations and functions, techno stress among employees, competence needs, security issues, Tele – working technological issues and lack of end user experience among employees. Further it discussed the implications for DEX are Setting the infra-structure, Tele-working necessary model equipment, Creating Positive DEX by streamlining digital tools and updates, Provision of end user experience to employees and competency needs among employees.

Keywords: Digital Workplace, Employee Experience, Individual Involvement, Digital Workspace

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Note

1. Digital Employee Experience

Digital Employee Experience (DEX) means the experience of employees while interacting with the workplace technology, digital tools, information technology systems and technology infrastructure. The experience is not only focusing the technology infrastructure and applications, but also mainly focusing on the intuitiveness, supportiveness and efficiency of the technology tools in helping the employees performing everyday duties and tasks. Boatman (2021) highlighted DEX is specifically, as interfacing with technologies for carry out the work activities and workflow, focusing productivity, efficient communication and collaboration, notably in learning the HR systems. A DEX solution considers every aspect of an employee's interactions with workplace environment like interactions with personal computer, printers and other devices, and software applications. DEX as a subset component of Employee Experience (Ex) captures the user experience of employees in the workplace with the technology that controls the everyday work performance (Firstup, 2021) (Sharmila Rani & Gerald Goh, 2022).

According to the ThoughtFarmer Intranet Blog (2022), DEX includes how employees interact with digital work environment that encompasses the tools, technologies' the employees use in the workplace, and the culture they follow within the work system. The organizations are responsible for need of digital infrastructure and arrangements, evaluating the employee experience with the digital tools and evaluating the experience of employees in accessing the digital tools and technologies in the workplace. Rani & Goh (2022) highlighted the insights of DEX as how the employees feel and perceive in interaction with digital technologies that the organizations design and access for efficiency. This is based on the purpose, need and credibility, ease of use, and how far the support of organizations. This would greatly impact on the employee engagement, retention, learning and productivity.

2. Objectives and Methodology

The study has the objectives to discuss the employee experience in the digital workplace and its importance for efficient functioning of the organization.

It is to discuss the practicality of the organizations while facing challenges. There are a few studies has dealt with DEX in a qualitative way of discussion. This study applied qualitative approach used literature survey method to collect the existing literatures related to DEX Digital Employee Experience, Need of DEX at present era, & sustainable digital workplace for sustainability of the organizations in the modern era. The study adopted qualitative literature review content analysis using summative method for discussing and reporting the need of digital workplace employee experience, challenges.

3. Employee Experience vs Digital Employee Experience

Employee experience can be defined as the interactions of employees and end to end journey of employees in the workplace with everything and everyone within an organization (Ludike, 2018, & Raia, 2017). Morgan (2015) discusses the components of employee experience as cultural, technological and physical structure. Culture aspects deals with the feelings of employees while getting connected with workplace the mood and the tone that workplace sets like leadership style, values, organizational structure. The technology aspects refer to the workplace technologies, tools, equipments, digital platforms for their jobs done. This includes devices, tools, software applications and digital transformation. The physical environment aspects refer to the physical aspects the employees in workplace touch, taste and smell in the workplace. All the three cultural, technological and physical structure enables to create employee experience whereas Digital employee experience as a subset of employee experience precisely captures the employees' user experience while having the interactions with company technology needed for workers to perform their jobs effectively, culture system that dominates employees' everyday work performance (Firstup, 2021).

4. DEX - Workplace Components

Digital employee experience encompasses the components by its nature that makes the employees to interact with technological advancements and digital work environment culture.

The components are like technology performance, automated process, increased work flexibility, increased productivity and real time evaluation, assessment and feedback, a) technology performance – it refers to the performance of technologies – systems and tools for assuring the speed, reliability and responsiveness as the foundation for user satisfaction and at what extent the earlier completion of work tasks with quality focus, Chandwani et al (2021), b) automated process – it refers to the automated process in work carry outs, tasks completions, meeting the demands and orders, on – boarding employees for need of work carry outs, customer satisfaction and others by using available technologies in integration of work functions (Sharmila Rani & Gerald Goh, 2022) work routines and encouraging interconnected networks, c) increased work flexibility – it refers to the flexibility nature of work tasks possible by using the technological advancements notably at office, work from home or hybrid mode of carrying out work tasks by using networking, cloud computing systems, file storage and transformation systems and so on, d) increased productivity – it refers to the constant consistent work tasks completion by accessing collaborative, communicative and integrative approach possible by using technological advancements like cloud computing, networking, mailing and so on, e) real time evaluation and feedback – it refers to automated evaluation and feedback mechanism for employee opinion, customer feedback for improvements through various software applications and networking platforms like surveys, online forms and so on.

5. Importance of DEX

Digital Employee Experience is quite significant in creating an employee a learner that digital thinker. The employee learns and executes the work process and work progress with the prime support of technologies (Sharmila Rani & Gerald Goh, 2022). They voluntarily engage in the work tasks and achievements since digital experience creates a work standard and comfort in ease access of work performance. Since the employees interact with technologies, it is easy to engage and retain the employees in work functions for longer period. Then, further, the digital employee experience, enables the employees to collaborative work culture since it is interconnected with all other departments,

it leads to flexible work arrangements like work at office, work from home or hybrid, it enables to reduce the operational cost since the workplace is digitally enabled and physically transformed to digital, Chandwani et al (2021), further it leads and compels the employees for continuous learning since the technology changes are permanent, and it has approach of data driven to decisions and working pattern and culture, it leads to process efficiency and productivity then it gives a competitive advantage to the company.

6. Digital Workplace

Digital workplace initiatives or the introduction of technology to improve the way employees interact and carry out tasks, can transform organizations and the ways in which people work Alexandre Diard (2022). Cost savings, increased productivity, process improvement and a happier workforce are all potential outcomes from a successful digital project.

7. Digital Workplace Tools for DEX

The digital workplace is a unified platform provides access to a large set of digital tools that are the software and technologies to perform the core work responsibilities. The tools support to employees for collaborating, communicating and performing the work responsibilities in an effective way in a digital work environment Atomicwork blog (2025). The tools support for remote and hybrid works by enabling real time interactions, project management, files and documents sharing and task automation. These are for streamlining the work process, workflow arrangements, resulting in more connected and productive teams (Sharmila Rani & Gerald Goh, 2022).

Collaboration and Communication – It is necessary in the workplace to communicate each other. The effective communication like messaging, instant messaging, video and audio chat is done by the digital tools like a) Slack – a powerful team messaging app with a wide range of features and customization that allows the work teams for creating workspaces, channels and tracking the documents & reviewing previous messages b) Google Hangouts – It allows the teams to chat with voice/video calls with other Google users and it can

be accessed through web or dedicated teams to chat with voice/video calls with other Google users and it can be accessed through web or dedicated mobile apps. The Gmail users also can access the handouts c) Face book in workplace – it is a collaborative tool to communicate for instant messaging and it allows the people to get connected socially in the workplace, Atomicwork blog (2025).

Project Management – The tool will be helping for streamlining the remote teams for upcoming works and tasks. It maintains transparency in workflow and it reduces back and forth emails. The tools are a) Base camp – focuses on team collaboration for every project to create a dedicated message board, to-do list, file manager, and calendar b) Asana – it helps the teams to breakdown the projects into smaller sections, tasks, and sub-tasks and it enables to select an assignee, due date, task description, and label c) Trello – allowing the users to organize projects in a kanban board format and streamlining the project workflow by creating custom lists and adding tasks in the form of cards d) Write – it offers a highly intuitive interface with a completely customizable dashboard. The tool allows users to edit documents on the cloud without the need to download them and it has the features like time tracking, task management, gantt chart, and third party integration, Atomicwork blog (2025).

Remote Desktop – This enables the remote access using desktop virtually from anywhere and it requires internet connection. This can be especially helpful for employees need to access information when they are outside the office. The tools are a) AnyDesk – a free access program runs in portable mode may be installed like any other software. It enables for transferring files and documents with speed and best quality b) Chrome Remote Desktop – created by google chrome and it is available on web and Android, easy set up and use, and it needs a Chrome browser to use it c) Remote PC – allows to manage and access multiple remote computers in real-time, record sessions and it enables to transfer files, view all the remote computer screens together, and play sound remotely and It can be accessed through the web, PC, or a mobile app, Kissflow blog (2024).

Time Management – It allows the employees to track the time they spend working, department heads can monitor employees, and even bill clients directly based on the total number of hours spent on the project.

There are the tools like a) Toggl – enables to start tracking time by clicking on a single button. For the different sections of time tracked, it can add a project, client, description, and label and enables to create separate workspaces for different teams and to extract in-depth reports based on app data b) Clockify – it uses a digital stopwatch to help users track time for every task, and allows the team leaders to allocate specific time duration for every project to make sure the employees stay on track, c) Harvest – another popular time tracking tool that allows to track time for different clients and projects and it enables for every project, send invoices, analyze data, and even submit the timesheets to the manager with the app, Atomicwork blog (2025).

Screen Sharing and Recording – the applications helps the team members understand and to have different perspectives and it is helpful for support teams working remotely to connect with clients and resolve their problems faster. The tools are a) Team Viewer – it is a remote access screen sharing tool with enterprise functionalities and it is primarily made for tech support teams, its interface makes the tool incredibly easy to use for all users and it includes collaborations with others, annotate reports, and record screen-sharing sessions that can be synced to the cloud b) Screen leap – simple screen sharing tool that can generate a permanent URL that can be shared with others easily with provided unique code, c) join .me – it is a screen sharing and video conferencing tool with advanced features like screen region sharing, annotation, and an interactive whiteboard and it is to create a custom URL or share the screen code with other team members, Kissflow blog (2024)

Video Conferencing & Tele Working – the primary way for team members to share work tasks for the meetings and communication. This is for meetings and collaborate sessions and discussion. This ideal video conferencing and Tele – working tool supports group chat for even your biggest teams, allow you to hold web seminars, and let employee record important calls. The tools are a) Skype – the most popular video calling apps in the market and it's still the quickest way to make a call for most Windows users. It comes pre-installed in Windows PCs, b) Zoom- it quickly become a new favorite of people for personal and work video calls and it allows free video calls with up to 50 people with a 40 minute call duration limit and it lets the

users record full-length videos, chat while a video call is going on, share the screen, draw on a whiteboard, and schedule calls in advance c) Cisco Webex – it is an enterprise grade video conferencing tool which is used by many leading companies and even governments around the world because of its reliability and security and it collaborates on a whiteboard and even annotate on the screen. It also works for larger meetings, allowing the broadcast videos to up to 3000 people, Atomicwork blog (2025).

Cloud Storage – It refers to the storage functions for storing the data in the form of files of various format and the suitable affordable tools enables to highly secure, and reliable. The tools are a) Google Drive - the default cloud storage app by most Gmail for integrative work tasks with google's other applications and it is importantly, it is closely integrated with Google Docs which allows users to quickly edit and save the Word, Powerpoint, and Excel files that they upload on the drive c) Dropbox – being a cloud storage app that was launched in the market to make it easy for users to share files and folders and it is for its interface, powerful file sharing features, and collaboration options have made it a cult favourite, d) One Drive – it is by Microsoft allows users to upload and sync data online, and access it from anywhere. It lets users edit files online due to its close integration with Office 365. It allows to access selected files offline, share files and folders with other users, scan documents, and sync offline folders on your PC to the cloud, Kissflow blog (2024).

8. Need of Digital Workplace

The operating philosophy of organizations can be changed responding to the digital modern workplace environment and improvement. The organizations understand the use of digital platforms and its advantages. There are many reasons for setting up a digital workplace in the digital era a) Increased Openness – it allows the teams of employees for centralized access to all the company tools, apps, and data by automating business operations and it enables the managers to monitor and control their organizations effectively and it allows the workers to go forward when there is more openness, which results in heightened controls, greater responsibility, and fewer file redundancies b) Enhanced Corporate Integration – the digital workplace provides options

to communicate with workers at all times in an efficient way. The digital tools enables for instant messaging, tracking, file sharing with speed and accuracy. It integrates every functional business actions easily c) Working remotely – the digital space enables for work remotely since it makes employees feel balanced work and life. The workers want to work on their own time and in their own place. It allows employees without compromising performance, d) Increasing operational productivity – The digital workspace leads to more meaningful work by automating, repetitive and administrative tasks. It allows for rapid access of files, data and material need for working remotely e) Boost employee participation – the modern digital workplace urges the workers to get into adopt and participate in the digital tool applications for business functional activities and work functions. It is inevitable for employees to participate in work activities with easy access of digital tools (Diard, 2022).

9. Digital Work Environment Challenges for DEX

Digital workplace has to create a big scope for DEX. Digital workplace includes the digital tools and applications for business and management functional operations. There are many research studies have evidenced that organizations face many challenges and issues in setting DEX suitable workplace. The challenges are following in the section.

The big challenge the digital workplace organization faces is to integrate the needs of the business with business operations and functions of local, global and international systems and practices. There will not be efficient tools and technologies to get integrated the global systems Raković et al (2022). If they have tools and technologies for managing the spread of business and reach of products, markets and suppliers, the organizations face the challenge of cost spending for integration in long run of business (Attaran et al., 2019).

Techno-stress in workplace while implementing digital tools update happens among employees that may result resistant to change, dissatisfaction and disengagement in work (Herbison, 2019) and the employees prefer to work with the old tools and applications (Moore, 2020).

Kalischko and Riedl (2021) reveal that the spread of technology in the workplace leads to technostress, which later can cause fatigue, burnout, depression and reduced employee satisfaction. Then the digital workplace gives scope for autonomy and monitoring employee performance (Gerten et al., 2019) that lead to loss of privacy (Brahma et al., 2021), which can result in reduced employee satisfaction. According to Kalischko and Redl (2021), frequently monitored employees are less satisfied with the job than those who are not monitored Raković et al (2022).

Need of competencies to access the digital workspace, there are insufficient internal sources for competency mapping and trainings for Individuals (Vallo Hult & Byström, 2021), which may become a challenge for organizations and individuals (Attaran et al., 2019). There is an increasing need for knowledge workers with specific digital competencies for selecting the digital tools and technologies suitable to business needs and functions (Erceg & Zoranović, 2020) (Brahma et al., 2021) (Vallo Hult & Byström, 2021)

Remote work culture and work from home may negatively impact on productivity, since they communicate and share everything digitally & through non organizational channels and they don't have physical conversations and sharing, since there is a chance of poor supervision and distractions from assigned tasks (Deloitte, 2020). This remote working culture may lead to create information silo and duplicate of work may negatively impact the productivity (Hicks, 2019).

Relationship issues - The digital workplace create scope for depending on digital tools for communication and collaboration and sharing, they will not have traditional way of physical communication and sharing, and it may lead to relationship problems and lead to loss of interpersonal skills, lack of interactions with new employees. (Corbin-Herbison, 2019), which can often cause a feeling of isolation and the loss of serendipity among employee relationship and innovation in workplace that is often associated with closer employee interaction (Deloitte, 2020).

Security Issues – the quite common challenge in digital workplace is the implementation of ICT tools and technologies with security. There is a question mark for data protection, intellectual property, on-going projects and so on (Attaran et al., 2019).

There are chances in the digital workplace for hacking and accidental leaks of data, information and secret details of the organizations and employees are unfamiliar with security protocols for exchange of information through intranet (Hicks, 2019).

Implementation of technology across various levels – since the lack of knowledge in selecting the right digital tools and applications and since the lack of competency among employees to access the digital tools and lack of interest to adopt, there are digital tool implementation issues happening in the workplace Attaran et al. (2019) highlighted the confusion in implementation across various levels of functions. The Dell and Intel Future Work Study Global report in 2016 revealed that more than 30 % of employees felt waste of time in tech-related issues which include slow, malfunction software or devices Raković et al (2022).

Tele- working technologies and collaboration – There are many digital workplaces don't have a proper Tele – working model for learning and development as a part of efficient ways of application of technology in workplace. The study of Haskins and Nilssen, as cited in Attaran et al. (2019), showed that the most of the digital workplaces have little or no teleconferencing and collaboration technologies in place for their meeting rooms, and highlighted technical difficulty as one of the main reasons for prolonged meetings Raković et al (2022). This state of being explains digital workplace is just for merging technology into business operations and activities rather than futuristic and development oriented.

End user experience among employees – Most of digital workplaces have the workplace restrictions while using new technologies that would limit the end user accessibility and it would the motivation and learning level of employees. Abhari et al. (2021) claimed that many organizations introduce new technology without direct input from end-users imposes restrictive digital governance that negatively affects the motivation of their employees. This fails to create disengagement among the employee.

Lack of support from employees responding to the new software update- the companies are spending huge amount of money for setting up digital workplace tools for DEX. It requires the support of employees but it is not possible all digital workplace tools for DEX.

It requires the support of employees but it is not possible all the time and all the situations. There are many reasons from employee side. They are getting addicted to digital platforms rather than manual or traditional, they require the software tools for all the occasions regarding task completion. This may create huge spending from company side, Nisha Sharma (2022).

Lack of software updates and time to time update – the employees getting into practice using the digital platforms, they require speedy software tools with modern updates but it will not happen all the times and all the occasions. They expect the updates and they are not ready to work in already existing software. They get frustrated without updated software. This may lead to impact the retention tendency of employees. This may enable to create the issue of adoptable quality of employees, Nisha Sharma (2022).

10. Strategic Implications to Create DEX

Responsibility of Organization to set the infrastructure – DEX requires a well-established infrastructure that would positively encourage employees to get connect with workplace. According to the ThoughtFarmer Intranet Blog (2022), DEX encompasses the way employees work, the required tools and technology they use, and the culture they exist within. Organizations should be the responsible for examining the infrastructure – the necessary tools and applications; employee interaction is to be encouraged – relationship maintenance for work sharing to complete the job tasks; and experiences – employee use technology in difficult and complex situations, whether they are creative and productive.

Tele-working necessary model equipment – Many organizations and employers use the digital technology as their contingency plan via Tele-working and tools such as video conferencing, cloud services, and virtual private networks. To improve the production levels, there is a need of creation of rapid and hybrid work culture (OECD, 2021).

Creating Positive DEX by streamlining digital tools and updates – There are the prime factors required for creating DEX to remain positive work environment.

First of all the relationship maintenance between the employees by open physical communication and sharing, creation of right digital tools and applications with proper training for employees, encouraging the employees for learning the workplace (Sasmitha et al., 2025) and getting into adopt the work environment and culture setting for sense of belongingness in the workplace. Then the employees have to be motivated to learn the update version of digital tools instead of using unfamiliar tools this would create the ways to streamline the digital tools and make them more simplified.

Provision of end user experience to employees – Attaran et al. (2019) and Morgan (2018) suggested to digital workplaces that should create end user exposure to the employees for using the digital tools and applications through various types of trainings like demonstration, displays, instructions and so on, and they suggest that the employees should feel and experience the benefits of using digital tools for work task solutions, organizations should provide employees with a consistent, consumer like user experience through consumer-grade technology Abhari et al. (2021) that is modern, forward thinking, engaging, and entirely aligned with the way people work today.

Framing of digital workplace strategic goals and plans and digital workforce execution planning, business and functional designing for digital workplace alignment and proper plan of execution for integrating local and global systems and having budget planning and cost spending may be rightly done and executed for facing the challenge of integration of needs of digital tools with business operations with local, global and international systems (Attaran et al., 2019).

The proper explanation of digital tools and applications across various functional levels and encouraging employees for learning the technologies for functional solutions through the arrangement of training programs (Sasmitha et al., 2025) and counseling, it may be reduced the Techno-stress among employees in workplace that may result satisfaction and engagement in work (Herbison, 2019). Kalischko and Riedl (2021) reveal that the spread of technology in the workplace leads to technostress, which later can cause fatigue, burnout, depression and reduced employee satisfaction.

Then the digital workplace gives scope for autonomy and monitoring employee performance (Gerten et al., 2019) that lead to loss of privacy (Brahma et al., 2021), which can result in reduced employee satisfaction. According to Kalischko and Redl (2021), frequently monitored employees are less satisfied with the job than those who are not monitored.

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11. Conclusion

The paper discussed the digital employee experience that is the experience of employees in interacting with technologies, tools and applications while doing every work functions. This is quite required at present digital era. This makes employees more confident, support, quick in completion of work, feeling standard of life and so on, in other hand there are may challenges like relationship issues, no network coverage, privacy issues, insecurity of data, setting the digital infrastructure, complexity in digital workplace management, techno stress and so on. The above-mentioned challenges have to be met by the organizations whether small, medium or large using strategic ways like digital workplace planning, framing business goals and functions aligned with digital automation, recruiting competent employees, training and developing them, encouraging digital workplace culture and system, having updates and supportive mechanisms for employees and so on. This digital workplace will hugely contribute the sustainability of the organizations.

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